

FEATURES AND FACTORS OF EMPLOYMENT FORMATION WITH TELEWORK IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

Toliboev Samad Tollyboy son

Sharaf Rashidov Samarkand state named after
university support doctoral candidate

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15580834>

Abstract. This article analyzes the content, characteristics, relevance and development opportunities of one of the most relevant concepts that has emerged in the labor market in the process of global digital transformation - remote work, as well as its development in the conditions of Uzbekistan. Based on world experience, reports of international organizations and practical experience during the pandemic, the economic, legal, sociocultural, organizational and technological aspects of remote work are highlighted. The necessary conditions and restrictions for the expansion of remote work in the labor market of Uzbekistan are also analyzed.

Keywords: Remote work, digital economy, labor market, economic efficiency, technological infrastructure, management system, legal framework

One of the most relevant concepts that has emerged in the labor market in the process of global digital transformation is the concept of remote work. In scientific literature, remote work (English: remote work, telework) is understood as the organization of the labor process between the employee and the employer using information and communication technologies, not being in the same geographical location. Remote work, by its very nature, means that the employee's activities are carried out independently of the workplace, from home, another city, or even another country.

In world practice, this concept is characterized by several main features:

- the employee does not come to the employer's office to work;
- uses digital tools (internet, email, online platforms) to perform work tasks;
- often independently sets working hours or works on a flexible schedule.

According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), telework is defined as work in which the main part of a worker's work is performed outside the employer's workplace and with the help of information and communication technologies. In addition, the OECD report notes that telework has played an important role in ensuring business continuity, reducing health risks and maintaining a stable workforce during the pandemic.

The concept of “remote work” is not fully developed in the national legislation of Uzbekistan, in particular, in the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, on the basis of temporary procedures and government

resolutions introduced during the pandemic years, practical experience of this form of work has been formed. For example, IT companies, service organizations, higher educational institutions have begun to operate in a remote work format. In this regard, the concept of remote work in Uzbekistan is being formed not only in accordance with foreign definitions, but also in accordance with the conditions of the national labor market, the level of technological development and legal framework.

There is also a difference between remote work and other forms of employment. While the traditional form of work involves the employee regularly coming to the office to work, remote work allows you to manage the work process from another location. In addition, the concepts of freelancing and remote work also differ: while freelancing is often a form of independent entrepreneurship, remote work represents a relationship between an employer and an employee based on an employment contract.

The concept of remote work is emerging as a new opportunity for the workforce in today's digital economy and a means of increasing productivity for employers. Therefore, studying this concept with a theoretical basis is important for developing new strategies in the Uzbek labor market.

Having defined the concept of remote work, it is important to understand its relevance in the modern economy, especially in the digital economy. Because remote work is seen not only as a result of technological opportunities, but also as a new phase of global economic trends.

The global pandemic (COVID-19) has fundamentally changed the way businesses work around the world. In the digital economy, manufacturing, services, trade, and education sectors have been forced to adopt new ways of working. According to a World Bank report, during the pandemic, about 40 percent of the workforce in developed countries switched to remote work, while in developing countries this figure was 20-25 percent.

The relevance of remote work is determined by the following aspects:

–ensuring business continuity: allows work to continue in situations that hinder access to offices and production sites (e.g., quarantine, natural disasters).

–Maintaining employee safety: In situations that pose a health risk, employees can continue to operate while staying at home.

–Reducing employers' costs: office space, utility bills, and maintenance costs are reduced.

–Globalization of the workforce: the workforce is recruited regardless of geographical boundaries, which allows employers to reach a wider market.

–Implementation of technological solutions: modern IT tools, digital platforms, and automated systems increase work efficiency.

Uzbekistan , this relevance was especially evident in the IT sector, the service sector, and higher education institutions. During the pandemic, universities were forced to switch to distance learning platforms, and government agencies to online service provision. At the same time, many IT companies transferred their employees to work from home, which formed a new work culture and management approaches.

In addition, the relevance of remote work is directly related to Uzbekistan's digital economy development strategies. The President's "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy identifies the development of IT infrastructure, digitization of jobs, and expansion of remote services as one of the main directions. This creates the basis for considering remote work not only as a temporary solution, but also as a model for long-term economic development .

In the digital economy, remote work is considered not only to ensure the continuity and security of work processes, but also as one of the important factors in increasing national economic competitiveness. Therefore, the relevance of this form of work should be deeply analyzed from a theoretical and practical perspective.

is recognized not only as a technologically new form, but also as a phenomenon that fundamentally changes the relationship between employee and employer , the management system, work efficiency, and incentive mechanisms.

Based on scientific sources and international experience, the following main characteristics of the formation of remote work can be distinguished .

Geographic independence. Remote work primarily creates the opportunity for both the employee and the employer to work independently of location. Workers can perform their duties from home, another city or country. This allows the labor market to expand beyond national borders to a global market.

Flexible working hours. While in traditional employment, employees are subject to fixed working hours and schedules , in remote work, employees can often set their own working hours or work a flexible schedule, as agreed with their employer. This allows the employee to balance work and personal life.

Management through online communication tools. In remote work, the work process is often managed through online tools (email, video conferencing, messengers). As a result, the amount of direct communication between the

employee and the employer decreases , and digital communication takes its place.

Focusing on results . In remote work, managers are increasingly shifting from process to outcome control. That is, the quality and timeliness of work performed becomes more important than how much time employees put into their work. This requires a rethinking of the concept of efficiency.

Dependence on technology . Remote work is completely dependent on technological tools, and without high-speed internet, online platforms, virtual workspaces, cloud storage services, and electronic document management systems, it is impossible to operate effectively.

Motivation and self- management. In remote work, the employee must rely more on self-management skills. Since external control and motivation are weak in this form , aspects such as internal motivation, professional responsibility, and time management become a priority.

Uzbekistan , these features are gradually taking shape in the IT, education, and service sectors. However, the development of remote work in the public services sector, industry, and agriculture is associated with technological, organizational, and legal constraints.

The emergence of remote work implies not only a change in the form of work, but also a fundamental renewal of work efficiency, management systems and incentive mechanisms. In this regard, an in-depth study of these features serves as an important basis for developing national strategies.

Any form of employment is the result not only of technological opportunity, but also of a complex of legal, economic, sociocultural, and organizational factors.

influence the formation of remote work employment .

Technological factors
(high-speed internet, IT platforms, digital infrastructure)

Legal factors (employment contracts, working hours, legal regulations)

Economic factors
(salary, cost savings, tax benefits)

Sociocultural factors
(mentality, family and work balance, community relations)

Organizational and management factors
(communication channels, monitoring, results-based evaluation)

Figure 1.4. Factors influencing the formation of remote work¹

1. Technological factors. The effectiveness of remote work primarily depends on the technological infrastructure. Without high-speed Internet, modern information and communication technologies (platforms such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Slack), cloud services, and electronic document management systems, remote work will be practically unsuccessful. Even in the conditions of Uzbekistan, differences in internet quality and technological infrastructure across regions remain one of the main obstacles to the development of remote work.

is directly related to aspects such as employment contracts, working hours, remuneration, and occupational safety. In Uzbekistan, legal regulations in this area are still insufficient, since the Labor Code does not fully regulate many aspects of remote work. In foreign experience (for example, in the USA and European countries), special legal norms for remote work have been introduced.

3. Economic factors. While teleworking allows employers to reduce costs (office, utility bills, workplace equipment), it helps employees save on transportation and food costs. At the same time, economic aspects such as the flexibility of the wage system and tax benefits also have a significant impact on the development of teleworking.

4. Sociocultural factors. The attitude of society and employees to remote work is also an important factor. While some cultures have low confidence in employees' independent work, others have a developed ability to motivate them through creative approaches and self-management. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the family environment, traditional views of society, and work culture also affect the formation of remote work.

5. Organizational and management factors. For remote work to be successful, it is necessary to reorganize the work process within the organization, introduce effective communication channels, and create results-based monitoring and evaluation systems. Uzbek companies are still at the initial stage in this regard, and many organizations are facing difficulties in transitioning from traditional management to virtual management.

The remote work model has the potential to radically change not only the relationship between the employee and the employer, but also the economic and social systems in a broader sense. World practice shows that the introduction of this model has a significant impact on labor productivity, job satisfaction, economic efficiency, and attitudes towards work in society. In the conditions of

Uzbekistan , studying the economic and social impacts of remote work also serves as an important scientific basis for formulating national strategies.

Conclusion.

The remote work form in the modern economy provides an opportunity not only to achieve technological innovation, but also to radically update the system of work efficiency, management, incentives and labor relations. In the conditions of Uzbekistan , remote work is gradually developing in the IT, education, service sectors, but its expansion to the industrial and public services sectors requires improving the technological infrastructure, supplementing the legal framework, transforming management processes and adapting the national work culture. Global experience shows that the remote work form serves to increase economic efficiency, job satisfaction, security and national competitiveness. Therefore, the development of strategic measures to develop remote work in Uzbekistan is urgent .

List of used literature:

1. International Labor Organization (ILO). (2021). Teleworking During the COVID-19 Pandemic and Beyond. Geneva: ILO Publications.
2. OECD. (2022). Remote Work and Productivity Report. Paris: OECD Publishing.
3. World Bank. (2021). Global Economic Prospects: Impacts of Remote Work in Developing Countries. Washington, DC: World Bank Group.
4. Deloitte Insights. (2023). The Future of Remote Work: Lessons from Global Best Practices. London: Deloitte.
5. Murodov, A., & Ergashev, D. (2020). Digital Economy and Labor Market Transformation in Uzbekistan. Tashkent: Ilm Ziyo Publishing House .

